

Effects of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* on Wistar Albino Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom

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Abstract

Snakebite is a significant public health issue in many African nations, yet effective treatment is often inaccessible due to the high cost and limited availability of antivenoms. This study evaluates the effects of *Cayratia japonica* root aqueous extract on toxicity induced by *Echis ocellatus* venom in male Wistar albino rats. A total of 20 rats (average weight: 225 ± 0.28 g) were divided into five groups: Group 1 (normal control) received distilled water; Group 2 received 0.055 mg/kg *E. ocellatus* venom without treatment; Groups 3, 4, and 5 received 0.055 mg/kg venom alongside 1000 mg/kg, 2000 mg/kg, and 0.6 mg/ml standard drug, respectively. Blood samples were collected for biochemical analysis, including antioxidant parameters, serum electrolytes (calcium and potassium), and clotting time. Phytochemical analysis of *C. japonica* root extract revealed alkaloids, saponins, terpenoids, steroids, tannins, carbohydrates, quinones, and glycosides, with GC-MS identifying 48 compounds, five of which have antivenom properties. A significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) levels, along with an increase in malondialdehyde (MDA) in the venom-only group (Group 2), indicating oxidative stress. However, Groups 3 and 4 showed significant increases in SOD levels ($p < 0.05$) compared to Group 2. These findings suggest that *C. japonica* root extract has potential as a novel anti-snake venom agent.

Keywords: antioxidants, anti-venom, envenomation, medical plants, oxidative stress and phytochemicals

1.0 Introduction

Snake envenomation remains a major but neglected public health problem in many developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where accurate epidemiological data are often difficult to obtain [1]. In Northern Nigeria, snakebite incidents are predominantly caused by venomous species such as vipers and *Naja* species, with *Echis ocellatus* and *Naja nigricollis* being the most medically significant [2]. Due to their high morbidity and mortality rates, snakebites pose a serious threat to public health, often

resulting in severe local tissue damage, permanent disability, or death [3].

Envenomation by *Echis* species is characterized by severe local effects, including swelling, blistering, hemorrhage, and necrosis, as well as systemic manifestations such as coagulopathy and neurotoxicity [4]. In Nigeria, approximately 90% of reported snakebite cases are attributed to *E. ocellatus*, with an estimated 60% of snakebite-related deaths resulting from severe envenoming, while many survivors suffer long-term disabilities of varying severity [5]. These outcomes are exacerbated by

delayed hospital presentation, limited access to healthcare facilities, and the high cost and scarcity of effective antivenoms, especially in rural communities.

Snake envenomation disproportionately affects impoverished rural populations, where traditional healing practices often serve as the first line of treatment [6]. The strong association between snakebite-related mortality and poverty highlights the urgent need for accessible, affordable, and locally available therapeutic alternatives. In this context, medicinal plants have gained increasing attention as potential sources of anti-venom agents, with several plant extracts demonstrating venom-neutralizing and antioxidant properties in preliminary studies [7,8].

Cayratia japonica, a perennial vine belonging to the family Vitaceae, is widely distributed across temperate regions of East Asia, including China, Korea, and Japan [9]. The aerial parts of *C. japonica* have been traditionally used in Chinese folk medicine for the treatment of jaundice, rheumatism, erysipelas, diarrhea, edema, and hematuria [10]. Despite its documented pharmacological activities, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, there is a paucity of scientific evidence regarding the potential antivenom effects of *C. japonica*, particularly its root extract, and no reported studies have evaluated its efficacy against *Echis ocellatus* venom-induced toxicity. Additionally, biochemical and antioxidant effects of *E. ocellatus* envenomation remain unexplored.

Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the protective effects of aqueous root extract of *Cayratia japonica* against *Echis ocellatus* venom-induced toxicity in Wistar albino rats, with specific focus on antioxidant status, serum electrolyte balance, and clotting time.

2.0 Reagents and Equipment

All reagents used for phytochemical screening were of analytical grade. These included Molisch's reagent, Salkowski's reagent, Shinoda's reagent, Dragendorff's reagent, Mayer's reagent, ferric chloride, sodium hydroxide, concentrated hydrochloric acid, alcoholic potassium hydroxide, distilled water, and silica gel (60–120 µm).

The equipment used in this study included an ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectrophotometer, a Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrophotometer (Shimadzu FTIR-8400S), and a Gas

Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS) system. Other equipment included an electronic analytical balance, chromatographic tanks and columns, and standard laboratory glassware such as beakers, test tubes, pipettes, and funnels.

2.1 Plant Sample Collection and Preparation

The roots of *Cayratia japonica* were collected in June 2023 from a forest located in Wawa, Borgu Local Government Area, Niger State, Nigeria (latitude 9°53'N and longitude 4°31'E), covering an estimated land mass of 16,200 km² [11].

The plant material was identified and authenticated by a taxonomist in the Department of Biological Sciences, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Nigeria. A voucher specimen (No. FUDMA/PSB/00238) was deposited in the university herbarium for future reference. The collected roots were washed thoroughly with clean water to remove debris, air-dried at room temperature, and ground into a coarse powder using a mechanical grinder. The powdered sample was passed through a sieve to obtain a uniform particle size as described by [12].

Extraction was carried out using the maceration method. One hundred gram (100 g) of the powdered root sample was soaked in 1,000 mL of distilled water for 48 h with intermittent stirring. The extract was filtered, and the filtrate was concentrated using a water bath. The concentrated extract was subsequently dried by lyophilization and stored in an airtight container until use.

2.2 Acquisition of Animals and Animal Housing

Twenty (20) male Wistar albino rats, weighing between 252 and 258 g, were obtained from the Department of Biological Sciences, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. The animals were housed in the Animal House of the Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria.

The rats were maintained under standard laboratory conditions, including a 12 h light/12 h dark cycle, ambient temperature, and adequate ventilation. They were fed with commercial rat pellets (Chukum Feeds, Kaduna) and had access to clean drinking water *ad libitum* throughout the study period. All animals were allowed to acclimatize to the laboratory environment

for seven (7) days prior to the commencement of the experiment to minimize stress-related effects.

2.3 Acquisition of *Echis ocellatus* Venom

A live *Echis ocellatus* (carpet viper) was obtained with the assistance of a trained field handler. The snake was housed in the herpetarium of the Department of Biological Sciences and maintained under standard conditions. It was fed appropriately and allowed to acclimatize for three (3) weeks prior to venom extraction. Venom was obtained by manual milking of the live snake according to the method described by [13]. The collected venom was air-dried, stored in sterile containers, and kept under appropriate conditions until required for experimental use.

2.4 Animal Grouping and Treatments

Twenty (20) male Wistar albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) were randomly assigned into five (5) experimental groups, with four (4) rats in each group:

Group 1 (normal control): Rats received distilled water orally.

Group 2 (venom control): Rats were administered *Echis ocellatus* venom at a dose of 0.055 mg/kg body weight via intraperitoneal injection without any treatment.

Group 3 (venom + extract, 1000 mg/kg): Rats were administered *E. ocellatus* venom (0.055 mg/kg, intraperitoneally) followed by oral administration of *Cayratia japonica* aqueous root extract at a dose of 1000 mg/kg body weight, 30 min after envenomation.

Group 4 (venom + extract, 2000 mg/kg): Rats were administered *E. ocellatus* venom (0.055 mg/kg, intraperitoneally) followed by oral administration of *C. japonica* aqueous root extract at a dose of 2000 mg/kg body weight, 30 min after envenomation.

Group 5 (venom + standard antivenom): Rats were administered *E. ocellatus* venom (0.055 mg/kg, intraperitoneally) followed by treatment with standard antivenom (premium ASV) at a dose of 0.6 mL/kg body weight, 30 min after envenomation [14].

2.5 Determination of the Median Lethal Dose (LD₅₀) of *Echis ocellatus* Venom

The median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of *Echis ocellatus* venom was determined based on the method described by [15]. The LD₅₀ value obtained from this

reference was used to select the sublethal dose of venom administered to the experimental animals in the present study.

2.6 Acute Toxicity Assessment of aqueous root extract of *Cayratia japonica*

The acute oral toxicity of the aqueous root extract of *Cayratia japonica* was evaluated according to the method described by [16] and [17]. In the initial phase of the study, three (3) male Wistar albino rats were randomly assigned into three groups, with one rat per group. The animals were orally administered single doses of the extract at 1,600, 2,900, and 5,000 mg/kg body weight, respectively. Following administration, the rats were observed continuously for the first 24 h for signs of toxicity, including behavioural changes and mortality.

2.7 Qualitative Phytochemical Screening of Aqueous Extract of *Cayratia japonica* Root

Qualitative phytochemical screening of the aqueous root extract of *Cayratia japonica* was carried out to detect the presence of secondary metabolites, including alkaloids, flavonoids, steroids, saponins, quinones, carbohydrates, terpenoids, tannins, and glycosides. The screening procedures were performed using standard methods as described by [18].

2.8 Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS) Analysis of Aqueous Extract of *Cayratia japonica* Root

The aqueous root extract of *Cayratia japonica* was analyzed using Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS). The analysis was performed using an Agilent gas chromatograph (Model 7890B) equipped with a capillary column (30 m × 250 μm × 0.25 μm) and coupled to an Agilent mass selective detector (Model 5977A). The GC–MS analysis was carried out following the method described by [19]. The mass spectra of the detected compounds were compared with those in the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) mass spectral library for compound identification.

2.9 Determination of Antioxidant Parameters of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* in Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom

The activities of antioxidant enzymes, including superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT), as well as the level of malondialdehyde (MDA), were

determined using standard biochemical methods as described by [20].

2.9.1 Estimation of Serum Electrolytes of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* in Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom

At the end of the experimental period, rats were humanely euthanized under deep anesthesia followed by cervical dislocation or decapitation. Blood samples were collected and processed immediately [21]. The samples were centrifuged at 2,500 rpm for 5 min to obtain serum, which was carefully separated for electrolyte analysis.

Serum sodium concentration was determined using a sodium reagent set (TECO Diagnostics), while serum potassium concentration was estimated using the turbidimetric tetraphenylborate (TPB) method with a commercial test kit (Química Clínica Aplicada S.A.), as described by [22].

2.9.2 Determination of Blood Clotting Time of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* in Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom

Blood clotting time was determined using a modified capillary tube method. Briefly, following treatment and at the end of the experimental period, fresh blood samples were collected from each rat via vein puncture under mild restraint [22,23]. Approximately 2mL of blood was allowed to flow into a clean, dry glass test tube maintained at room temperature. A stopwatch was started immediately after blood collection, and the tube was gently tilted at 30-second intervals until the blood ceased flowing upon inversion, indicating clot formation. The time elapsed from blood collection to clot formation was recorded as the clotting time.

2.9.2 Statistical Analysis

All data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) from triplicate determinations. Statistical analyses were performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with GraphPad Prism software (version 8.0; GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). Differences among groups were considered statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Acute Oral Toxicity of *Cayratia japonica* Root Extract

Administration of the aqueous root extract of *Cayratia japonica* at doses up to 5,000 mg/kg body weight did not result in mortality in Wistar albino rats. Mild signs such as rough hair coat were observed only at the highest dose. These findings indicate that the extract has a high safety margin, with an oral median lethal dose (LD_{50}) greater than 5,000 mg/kg body weight. According to OECD toxicity classification, substances within this range are considered practically non-toxic, supporting the suitability of the extract for further pharmacological evaluation.

3.2 Phytochemical Composition and GC-MS Profile of aqueous extract of *Cayratia japonica* root

Qualitative phytochemical screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, phenols, steroids, carbohydrates, quinones, glycosides, and terpenoids in the aqueous root extract of *Cayratia japonica* (Table 1). These secondary metabolites have been widely reported to exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antivenom-related activities., this is inline with the findings of [7,8,6,23].

Table 1: Phytochemicals detected in aqueous extract of *Cayratia japonica* root

Phytochemicals	Status
Alkaloid	+
Saponin	+
Terpenoid	+
Steroid	+
Tannin	+
Flavonoid	-
Carbohydrate	+
Quinone	+
Glycoside	+
Phenol	+

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis identified forty-eight (48) compounds in the extract (Table 2; Figure 1). Some of the major compounds detected, including butylated hydroxytoluene, 9-octadecenamamide (Z), and 9,12-octadecadienoic acid, have been previously associated with antioxidant and venom-neutralizing properties [24]. The presence of these compounds may contribute synergistically to the observed protective effects against *Echis ocellatus* venom-induced toxicity [25].

Table2: Bioactive compounds detected in aqueous extract of *Cayratia japonica* root

S/N	RT	Area Pct	IUPAC	STRUCTURE	MOL. FORMULA	MOL.W T
1	5.5757	2.3125	Dehydromevalonic lactone		C6H8O2	112.13
2	7.8001	2.457	2H-Pyran-2-one, 5,6-dihydro-6-propyl-		C8H12O2	140.18
3	8.2357	1.3144	2H-Pyran-2-one, tetrahydro-6-propyl-		C8H14O2	142.20
4	8.5963	2.2093	dl-Mevalonic acid lactone		C6H10O3	130.14
5	8.6342	2.6137	dl-Mevalonic acid lactone		C6H10O3	130.14
6	8.8745	1.1375	dl-Mevalonic acid lactone		C6H10O3	130.14
7	8.9837	0.2754	dl-Mevalonic acid lactone		C6H10O3	130.14
8	9.0317	0.2499	2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl-		C13H26O	198.34
9	9.9978	0.3279	3-Methyl-1-diisopropylsilyloxybutane		C11H26OSi	202.41
10	10.1021	0.2154	3-Methyl-1-diisopropylsilyloxybutane		C11H26OSi	202.41
11	10.1498	0.0622	.beta.-D-Glucopyranose, 1-thio-,1-[N-hydroxy-5-(methylthio)pentanimidate]		C12H21NO10S2	403.43
12	10.5182	1.6923	Butane, 2,2'-thiobis-		C8H18S	146.29
13	10.6714	2.5207	1,2,3,4-Butanetetrol, [S-(R*,R*)]-		C4H10O4	122.12
14	10.8966	0.3502	1,2,3,4-Butanetetrol, [S-(R*,R*)]-		C4H10O4	122.12

S/N	RT	Area Pct	IUPAC	STRUCTURE	MOL. FORMULA	MOL.W T
15	10.9957	0.0456	2-Pentanethiol		C5H12S	104.21
16	13.0191	0.3198	D-Arabinitol		C5H12O5	152.15
17	13.5607	10.216 3	Butylated Hydroxytoluene		C15H24O	220.35
18	14.3302	6.0331	4-(3-Oxocyclohexyl)butyric acid, methyl ester		C11H18O3	198.26
19	14.569	3.4758	.beta.-D-Glucopyranose, 4-O-.beta.-D-galactopyranosyl-		C12H22O11	342.30
20	15.4012	9.0076	3-Morpholinopropyl 2,4-dihydroxybenzoate		C14H19NO5	281.30
21	17.0316	1.6202	2-Cyclohexen-1-one, 4-(3-hydroxy-1-butenyl)-3,5,5-trimethyl-, [R-[R*,R*-(E)]]-		C13H20O2	208.30
22	17.703	0.8435	Phensuximide		C11H11NO2	189.21
23	18.3521	1.113	Benzene, (5-iodopentyl)-		C11H15I	274.14
24	19.0434	4.5308	Benzene, 1,1'-(1,2-cyclobutanediyl)bis-, trans-		C16H16	208.30
25	20.672	6.4707	Chloroacetic acid, 4-methoxyphenyl ester		C9H9ClO3	200.62
26	22.6995	0.8664	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester		C17H34O2	270.45

S/N	RT	Area Pct	IUPAC	STRUCTURE	MOL. FORMULA	MOL.W T
27	24.0511	0.8376	Hexadecanoic acid, ethyl ester		C18H36O2	284.48
28	25.9689	3.4571	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester		C19H34O2	294.47
29	26.0777	2.2453	9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, methyl ester		C19H36O2	296.49
30	27.2092	0.3122	9,12-Octadecadienoyl chloride, (Z,Z)-		C18H31ClO	298.89
31	27.313	2.321	(E)-9-Octadecenoic acid ethyl ester		C20H38O2	310.51
32	27.8195	0.606	Octadecanoic acid, ethyl ester		C20H40O2	312.53
33	30.9898	1.6309	9-Octadecenamide, (Z)-		C18H35NO	281.48
34	32.1741	3.6252	.alpha.-Benzylsuccinic acid		C11H12O4	208.21
35	32.6677	3.2809	9-Octadecenal, (Z)-		C18H34O	266.46
36	33.0863	0.1856	9-Oxabicyclo[6.1.0]nonane, cis-		C8H14O	126.20
37	33.6644	2.4757	(2,3-Diphenylcyclopropyl)methyl phenyl sulfoxide, trans-		C22H20OS	332.46
38	33.8996	5.5044	1-Propene, 3-(2-cyclopentenyl)-2-methyl-1,1-diphenyl-		C21H22	274.40
39	34.2119	1.6006	Naphthalene, 1,2-dihydro-2-methyl-		C11H12	144.21
40	35.416	0.4776	17-Octadecynoic acid		C18H32O2	280.45
41	35.6309	0.5425	Adipic acid, isobutyl trans-2-methylcyclohexyl ester		C17H30O4	298.42
42	35.8767	0.3682	cis-11-Hexadecenal		C16H30O	238.41

S/N	RT	Area Pct	IUPAC	STRUCTURE	MOL. FORMULA	MOL.W T
43	36.2965	6.4386	2-Methyl-Z,Z-3,13-octadecadienol		C18H34O	266.46
44	36.7279	0.6034	9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester		C21H40O4	356.54
45	37.8004	1.0421	1,5,9-Undecatriene, 2,6,10-trimethyl-, (Z)-		C14H24	192.34
46	37.972	0.0109	Oleic Acid		C18H34O2	282.46
47	38.3889	0.0874	Oleic Acid		C18H34O2	282.46
48	38.5469	0.2405	cis-11-Hexadecenal		C16H30O	238.41

Figure 1. GC-MS chromatogram of aqueous root extract of *Cayratia japonica*

3.3 Effects of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* on Antioxidant Parameters in Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom

Envenomation with *Echis ocellatus* venom resulted in a significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) activities, along

with a significant increase in malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, compared to the control group (Table 3). This indicates severe oxidative stress, consistent with the known ability of snake venom to generate reactive oxygen species and disrupt cellular antioxidant defence systems[26] and[27]

Table 3. Effects of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* on Antioxidant Parameters in Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom

Groups	SOD(U\ml)	CAT(U\ml)	MDA(nmol\mL)
Group 1	10.37±1.13 ^a	7.10±1.80 ^a	42.8±8.33 ^a
Group 2	3.97±0.27 ^b	2.03±0.07 ^b	175.2±2.10 ^b
Group 3	6.27±0.28 ^c	5.03±0.33 ^c	52.87±1.68 ^c
Group 4	5.97±0.17 ^d	3.97±0.23 ^d	50.10±0.00 ^d
Group 5	6.40±0.40 ^c	3.10±0.10 ^c	59.17±4.83 ^c

Values with the same superscript alphabet in the same column are not significantly different
Values are Means ± SEM of four duplicate.

Key: Group 1: control; Group 2: venom untreated; Group 3: venom and treated with 1000 mg/kg bw. of extract; Group 4: venom and treated with 2000 mg/kg bw. of extract; Group 5: venom and treated with 0.6 ml/kg of standard drug.

Treatment with *C. japonica* root extract significantly restored SOD and CAT activities and reduced lipid peroxidation in a dose-dependent manner. These effects suggest that the extract enhances endogenous antioxidant defences, likely due to its rich content of phenolic compounds, alkaloids, and unsaturated fatty acids identified in the phytochemical and GC-MS analyses[2]. The antioxidant effects observed were comparable, in part, to those of the standard antivenom, this agreed with the findings of [28].

3.4 Effects of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* on Serum Electrolytes concentration in Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom

Rats exposed to *Echis ocellatus* venom showed a significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in serum calcium and potassium concentrations respectively relative to the control group (Table 4). This indicates venom-induced disruption of electrolyte homeostasis. Such alterations are known complications of viper envenomation and may contribute to neuromuscular and cardiovascular dysfunction[29] and[30].

Table 4. Effects of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* on Serum Electrolytes concentration in Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom

Group	Calcium(mg\dl)	Potassium(mmol\l)
Group 1	2.83±0.27 ^a	86.68±0.83 ^a
Group 2	1.43±0.07 ^b	39.10±3.00 ^b
Group 3	2.40±0.10 ^c	74.37±1.93 ^c
Group 4	2.57±0.23 ^d	66.47±4.07 ^d
Group 5	2.43±0.03 ^c	74.80±2.70 ^c

Values with the same superscript alphabet in the same column are not significantly different
Values are Means ± SEM of four duplicate.

Key: Group 1: control; Group 2: venom untreated; Group 3: venom and treated with 1000 mg/kg bw. of extract; Group 4: venom and treated with 2000 mg/kg bw. of extract; Group 5: venom and treated with 0.6 ml/kg of standard drug.

Administration of *C. japonica* root extract significantly improved serum calcium and potassium levels, with the higher dose producing greater restoration. This dose-dependent response suggests that the extract mitigates venom-induced metabolic disturbances and supports physiological recovery. The electrolyte-restoring effect of the extract was comparable to that observed with the standard antivenom[31]

3.5 Effects of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* on Blood Clotting Time in Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom

Echis ocellatus venom significantly prolonged blood clotting time in untreated rats (Figure 2), reflecting its hemotoxic nature and interference with coagulation pathways[32], [33]. Treatment with *C. japonica* root extract significantly reduced clotting time in a dose-dependent manner, indicating partial neutralization of venom-induced coagulopathy.

Figure 2. Effects of Aqueous Root Extract of *Cayratia japonica* on Blood Clotting Time in Rats Exposed to *Echis ocellatus* Venom Effect on Blood Clotting Time

Although the standard antivenom demonstrated superior efficacy, the extract produced a marked improvement compared to the untreated group, suggesting potential complementary value in managing venom-induced bleeding disorders. This is in accordance with [34]

4.0 Conclusion

This study demonstrated that the aqueous root extract of *Cayratia japonica* exhibits protective effects against *Echis ocellatus* venom-induced toxicity in Wistar albino rats. The extract showed a high margin of safety and contained several bioactive phytochemicals with reported antioxidant and antivenom-related properties.

Administration of the extract significantly improved antioxidant enzyme activities, reduced lipid peroxidation, restored serum electrolyte balance, and shortened venom-induced prolonged clotting time. These effects were dose-dependent and comparable, in part, to those observed with the standard antivenom.

Although the extract did not completely neutralize all toxic effects of the venom, the findings suggest that *Cayratia japonica* root extract may serve as a promising complementary or adjunct therapeutic agent in the management of snakebite envenomation. Further studies involving venom enzyme inhibition assays, isolation of active compounds, and clinical validation are recommended to confirm its antivenom potential.

References

1. Ammouch K, Mesmoudi N, Hammani N, Galan J, Moustaghfir A, Stöcklin R, et al. Tackling the burden of envenomation in Africa: advances, challenges, and strategic priorities for enhanced diagnosis and treatment. *Front Trop Dis.* 2025;6, article ID 1653213. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fitd.2025.1653213>.
2. Gbolade AA. Nigerian medicinal plants with anti-snake venom activity: a review. *J Malaria Res Phytomed.* 2021;1(1):1–10.
3. Mahendra M, Mujtaba M, Mohan CN, Ramaiah M. Study of delayed treatment perspective of snake bites and their long-term effects in a tertiary care hospital in Bagalkot district of Karnataka. *APIK J Intern Med.* 2021;9(3):153–8.
4. Yusuf PO, Ada D, Nuhu DB, Dahiru S, Ameh PM, Mamman M, et al. Toxicopathological effects of the venom of *Echis ocellatus* on experimentally envenomated Swiss albino rats. *J Appl Sci Environ Manage.* 2024;28(12 Suppl):4357–65.
5. Michael GC, Grema BA, Bala AA, Olawumi AL, Gana AA, Madaki JKA, et al. Lifetime prevalence and knowledge of snakebite among graduates in Nigeria. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg.* 2023;117(7):505–13. doi:10.1093/trstmh/trad006.
6. Aron MB, Mulwafu M, Mailosi B, Kreuels B, Dullie L, Kachimanga C, et al. Experiences and practices of traditional healers on snakebite treatment and prevention in rural Malawi. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2023;17(10):e0011653. doi:10.1371/journal.pntd.0011653.
7. Philip AM, Ofemile Y, Oluwatobi AI, Gabriel A, Ejiofor UP, Aske O. Medicinal plants used for the neutralization of snake venom in Northern Nigeria of West Africa. *Recent Pat Biotechnol.* 2023;17(1):3–8. doi:10.2174/1872208316666220426120228.
8. Puzari U, Fernandes PA, Mukherjee AK. Pharmacological re-assessment of traditional medicinal plants-derived inhibitors as antidotes against snakebite envenoming: a critical review. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2022;292:115208. doi:10.1016/j.jep.2022.115208.
9. Parmar G, Dang VC, Rabarijaona RN, et al. Phylogeny, character evolution and taxonomic revision of *Causonis*, a segregate genus from *Cayratia* (Vitaceae). *Taxon.* 2021;70(6):1188–218.
10. Akram M, Michael OS, Saeed M, et al. Ethnopharmacological properties of Asian medicinal plants during conflict-related blockades. In: *Phytochemistry, the Military and Health.* Elsevier; 2021. p. 53–68.
11. Salihu SC, Musa S, Aliyu S, Abdulmumini H. Determination of some physicochemical parameters and selected heavy metals in borehole water samples from Wawa town, Borgu LGA, Niger State, Nigeria. *Int J Sci Res Publ.* 2022;12(8):329–35. doi:10.29322/IJSRP.12.08.2022.p12840.
12. Basim GB, Khalili M. Particle size analysis on wide size distribution powders: effect of sampling and characterization technique. *Adv Powder Technol.* 2015;26(1):200–7.
13. Goswami PK, Samant M, Srivastava RS. Snake venom, anti-snake venom and potential of snake venom. *J Pharm Biol Sci.* 2014;9(2):55–63.
14. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). *Acute oral toxicity – fixed dose procedure (TG 420).* Paris: OECD; 2001. p. 1–14.
15. Adeyi AO, Adeyemi SO, Effiong EOP, Ajisebiola BS, Adeyi OE, James AS. *Moringa oleifera* extract attenuates *Echis ocellatus* venom-induced toxicities, histopathological impairments and inflammation via enhancement of Nrf2 expression in rats. *Pathophysiology.* 2021;28(1):98–115. doi:10.3390/pathophysiology28010009.
16. Lorke D. A new approach to practical acute toxicity testing. *Arch Toxicol.* 1983;54(4):275–87.
17. Garrido-Acosta O, Meza-Toledo SE, Anguiano-Robledo L, Valencia-Hernández I, Chamorro-Cevallos G. Adaptation of Lorke's method to determine and compare ED50 values: the cases of two anticonvulsant drugs. *J Pharmacol Toxicol Methods.* 2014;70(1):66–9.
18. Yahaya OT, Oladele EO, Bunza MDA, Yusuf AB, Izuafa A, Danjuma JB, et al. Hematotoxicity and nephrotoxicity of long-term administration of *Guiera senegalensis* (J.F. Gme), *Cassia occidentalis* (Linn), and *Ziziphus mauritiana* (Lam) leaves obtained in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria. *J Herbmed*

- Pharmacol. 2022;11(3):367-374. doi: 10.34172/jhp.2022.42.
19. Luedemann A, Strassburg K, Erban A, Kopka J. TagFinder for the quantitative analysis of GC-MS-based metabolite profiling experiments. *Bioinformatics*. 2008;24(5):732-7. doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btn023.
20. Hamam H, Demir H, Aydın M, Demir C. Determination of antioxidant activities and oxidative stress levels in cirrhotic liver patients. *Middle Black Sea J Health Sci*. 2022;8(4):506-14.
21. Aguwa US, Eze CE, Obinwa BN, et al. Comparing the effect of methods of rat euthanasia on the brain of Wistar rats. *J Adv Med Med Res*. 2020;32(17):8-16.
22. Asirvatham R, Nediya PP, Pa D. Protective effects of *Pluchea lanceolata* on dementia induced by omeprazole in experimental rats. *J Cell Neurosci Oxid Stress*. 2022;13(3):xxx-xxx.
23. Alsaedi S, Aljeddani G. Phytochemical analysis and bioactivity screening of primary and secondary metabolic products of medicinal plants in the valleys of Medina region, Saudi Arabia. *Adv Biol Chem*. 2022;12(4):92-115. doi:10.4236/abc.2022.124009.
24. Adamu M, Uttu AJ, Ajala A, Obansa RM, Madumelu M. A short review on plants used as anti-snake venom. *J Chem Rev*. 2023;5(3):341-52.
25. Yusuf AJ, Aleku GA, Bello UR, Liman DU. Prospects and challenges of developing plant-derived snake antivenin natural products: a focus on West Africa. *ChemMedChem*. 2021;16(24):3635-48. doi:10.1002/cmde.202100478.
26. Resiere D, Mehdaoui H, Neviere R. Inflammation and oxidative stress in snakebite envenomation: a brief descriptive review and clinical implications. *Toxins (Basel)*. 2022;14(11):802.
27. Marinho AD, Silveira JAM, Chaves Filho AJM, et al. Bothrops pauloensis snake venom-derived phospholipases A₂ mediate acute kidney injury by oxidative stress and inflammatory cytokine release. *Toxicon*. 2021;190:31-8.
28. Adrião AAX, Santos AO, Lima EJSP, et al. Plant-derived toxin inhibitors as potential candidates to complement antivenom treatment in snakebite envenomations. *Front Immunol*. 2022;13:842576.
29. Hussain SS, Kingsley JD. Metabolomics and proteomics: synergistic tools for understanding snake venom inhibition. *Arch Toxicol*. 2025;99:915-34.
30. Pavuluri LA, Bitla AR, Vishnubotla SK, Rapur R. Oxidative stress, DNA damage, inflammation and endothelial dysfunction in snakebite-induced acute kidney injury. *Indian J Nephrol*. 2025;35(3):349-54.
31. Jorge ARC, Marinho AD, Silveira JAM, et al. Phosphodiesterase-5 inhibitor sildenafil attenuates kidney injury induced by *Bothrops alternatus* snake venom. *Toxicon*. 2021;202:46-52.
32. Zeng FY, Ji RS, Yu XQ, Li YN, Zhang QY, Sun QY. A novel snake venom C-type lectin-like protein modulates blood coagulation. *Sci Rep*. 2024;14:22962.
33. Sun QY, Wang CE, Li YN, Bao J. Inhibition of platelet aggregation and blood coagulation by a P-III class metalloproteinase purified from *Naja atra* venom. *Toxicon*. 2020;187:223-31.
34. Okumu M, Mbaria J, Gikunju J, Mbutia P, Madadi V, Ochola F. Exploring nature's antidote: inhibitory potential of selected medicinal plants against snake venom. *Front Pharmacol*. 2024;15:1369768.

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